

Analysis of the Language Ability of Children Aged 4-5 Years at TK Pelangi Medan For Academic Year 2022/2023

Yola Lukita Saragih^{1*}, Dorlince Simatupang²
State University of Medan

Corresponding Author: Yola Lukita Saragih yolalukita456@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This training aims to improve skills in writing a curriculum vitae (CV) and facing job interviews for students at MAN 1 Brebes. The entry of students into the world of work requires good preparation in compiling an attractive CV and facing job interviews with confidence. Training and mentoring methods were used in this study, involving students in effective CV writing exercises and simulated job interviews. The results of the training showed a significant increase in students' ability to write an attractive CV and face job interviews with higher self-confidence. It is hoped that the results of this research can make a positive contribution to the preparation of students for facing challenges in the world of work and increase their chances of getting the job they want.

INTRODUCTION

The world of employment with a thousand job openings is not commensurate with the thousands, or even millions, of applicants. Competition among applicants is intense, ranging from those with no experience to those with extensive experience. Furthermore, many companies in Indonesia have already implemented a contract employment system.

Recruitment is a process comprising a series of activities used to select suitable candidates or prospective employees (Mahmud, 2017). One of the key factors that pique a company's interest in job applicants begins with the Curriculum Vitae (CV) or Resume and the job application letter or Cover Letter, which can be sent via email or postal mail.

Additionally, the interview stage plays a pivotal role in determining a company's interest in applicants. The most commonly employed method for selecting employees is the job interview. It can be said that most jobs are obtained after applicants have undergone the interview process (Wayan et al., 2022).

An interview is a communication transaction that emphasizes questions and answers. Since the interview aims to gather information, it occurs when the interviewer asks questions to learn about the interviewee's opinions, knowledge, attitudes, experiences, and other aspects (Ferlina, 2022). Interviews are typically conducted one-on-one between the interviewer and the applicant, but they can also take place between a group of applicants and one or two interviewers. Questions may be structured, unstructured, a mix of both, problem-solving, or designed to induce stress (Sari, 2022).

In this era of globalization and industrial revolution, for prospective graduates of Vocational High Schools (SMK) who wish to enter the workforce, there are many preparations to be made. It requires not only hard skills but also the soft skills demanded by companies, as well as adequate administrative documents. The Curriculum Vitae (CV) and job application letter create the first impression that companies see when recruiting new employees.

Therefore, the lecturers of the DIII Electronics Engineering program will organize training on creating Curriculum Vitae (CV) and job interviews as an effort to enhance the ability to write Curriculum Vitae (CV) and prepare for job interviews."

LITERATURE REVIEW

Understanding Language Ability

Language is a tool for conveying information, ideas, intentions, and notions which can be verbal or in written form. According to Warisman (Albaburahim, 2019) language is a symbol of society which gives rise to a variety of languages as a distinction between one society and another, both the social diversity of speakers and the diversity of language functions. According to Islamiati (2020), Language plays an important role in daily activities because it becomes the center for the interlocutor to understand or express the interlocutor's thoughts so that they are easily understood. According to Jahja (2011), language skills are a communication tool that allows the expression of feelings to the interlocutor as well as procedures for the interlocutor's thoughts

which are based on writing, gestures, oral, writing, numbers, and facial expressions.

Language Development of Children Aged 4-5 Years

Language is the basis for a child to be able to learn other things. Before children learn other knowledge, they also need to use language so they can understand it well. Language development is related to cognitive development, which means factors that greatly influence the development of language skills (Mursid, 2018). Since infancy, children already have language skills. No matter how simple it is, babies can pick up on sounds or signs given by people-closest people in their environment. In early childhood, language development begins to appear at the age of 1 year, when children start to chatter (the meaning is not yet clear). Language development has parts or aspects that must be considered, namely listening, speaking, writing, and reading. Children's listening skills have been stimulated since in the womb through efforts to listen to words or sentences that are good for children. A child's listening skills will influence his speaking ability, the results of a child's listening will be applied through his/her lips.

According to the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 05 of 2022 concerning National Standards for Early Childhood Education which are used as indicators to determine the level of language achievement in early childhood, namely: being able to listen, having awareness of text messages, the alphabet and phonemics, having basic skills. required to write, understand simple instructions, be able to express questions and ideas, and be able to use language skills to work together.

Language development in children aged 4-5 years, In choosing their vocabulary they will develop extraordinary and use complex sentences. Dwi (2015) said that the language development of children aged 4-5 years includes: 1) speaking fluently in simple sentences, 2) saying as many names of objects, animals, and plants that have certain colors, shapes, or according to certain characteristics, 3) talking about events around him simply, 4) sorting and telling the contents of the gambier series, 5) telling stories about pictures he made himself, 6) following 1 to 2 commands at once, 7) making as many words as possible from the initial syllables provided in a verbal form such as ma mama, embarrassed, angry and so on.

Characteristics of language abilities of early childhood children 4-5 years old

According to Anita Yus (2011), the language characteristics of children aged 4-5 years are: a) Differentiating sounds from several sources, b) telling stories using sentences consisting of three-six words with expressions, c) Carrying out three-five commands at once, d) Vocabulary is increasing, e) Asking questions with complex words (why and how), f) Reading pictures with the correct sentence structure, g) Starting to be able to dialogue and argue. The language characteristics of children aged 4-5 years are that they can pronounce more than 1,900 vocabulary words and the range of vocabulary that children can speak concerns color, size, shape, taste, smell, and beauty, Children aged 4-5 years can already participate in a conversation. Children can already listen to

other people talking and respond to those conversations according to Jamaris Martin (2014). Ahmad Susanto (2014) stated the characteristics of the language abilities of children aged 4-5 years, namely: a) children can use sentences well and correctly, b) master 90 percent of language phenomena and syntax, c) can carry out conversations by listening to other people speak and then respond.

The main characteristics seen in the research were the ability to listen and the ability to tell stories in children aged 4-5 years.

a. Listen

Listening is a stage that someone does from an early age. The role of listening is very important for the acquisition and development of language in children. Listening is the process of listening to verbal symbols with interpretation, appreciation, understanding, and attention to capture information, understand the meaning of the message, and understand the meaning of communication by the speaker whose source is spoken language (Tarigan, 2008). Listening is related to hearing and listening. Listening skills are an essential part of language because listening skills are the basis for language mastery. The supporting factor for students' reading fluency is listening skills. As a student, you can listen intensively according to Cigerci & Gultekin (Rahman. H 2019). Listening ability is part of understanding language which is divided into several indicators according to Madyawati (2013: 3), namely 1. listening and distinguishing sounds in Indonesian, 2. listening and distinguishing types of sounds simultaneously, 3. asking questions clearly, 4 Get to know the vocabulary regarding adjectives.

b. Speak

Speaking is the ability to utter articulatory sounds or words for feelings, and ideas, conveying thoughts, stating, and expressing (Tarigan 2015). Speaking is a skill that a person must have before he can speak the language well. Hurlock (2005) said that speaking is not the same as language. Language includes all means of communication by interpreting thoughts and feelings to convey meaning to other people. Speaking is not just an achievement for children but also aims to achieve its main goals, namely:

1. As a tool to find the center of other people's attention
2. As a tool for fostering social relationships
3. As a tool to satisfy needs and desires
4. As a tool for self-evaluation
5. As a tool to influence the thoughts and feelings of other people
6. To influence other people's behavior (Mulyani Sumantri & Nana

Syaodih 2014)

Factors that influence children's language development

Language is the most important tool in communication. By speaking, a person can develop the ability to get along with the people around him. According to Hilda (2018), factors that influence the development of children's language skills explain that several main factors influence the development of

language skills in early childhood, including health, intelligence, family economic status, gender, and parental relationships.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses descriptive methods and a qualitative approach. Qualitative research is carried out in natural conditions. Qualitative research is descriptive, namely research that provides descriptive data, namely writing or speech, and behavior that can be seen from the subject. The research raises problems through data. Data is viewed by joint observation, including descriptions in detailed context with notes from interviews, and the results of document and note analysis.

The subjects of this research were children aged 4-5 years (Class A) with a total of 4 children at Kindergarten Pelangi Medan. The object of this research is the language skills of early childhood children aged 4-5 years at TK Pelangi Medan. Tk Pelangi Medan which is located on Jln. Bhayangkara no. 147, Indra Kasih, Kec. Medan Tembung, Medan City, North Sumatra.

The data collection technique in this research is observation. Observation is one method that can be used directly by observing an object phenomenon that is observed objectively and systematic recording will be carried out to obtain a concrete picture of field conditions.

The data analysis technique used in this research is qualitative analysis. According to Miles and Huberman (in Sugiyono, 2014), data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and the final steps, namely concluding. These steps are as follows:

a. Data reduction

Data reduction is a summary of the data obtained from the field, selecting the main things and focusing on the important things so that conclusions can be drawn and can be drawn and verified. Data reduction will continue after field research until the final report is prepared. The data that will be reduced in this research is the language skills of early childhood children aged 4-5 years.

b. Data presentation

The presentation of data in qualitative research used in presenting research data is narrative text. Presenting data is the most important method in qualitative research. The presentation of this data is an arrangement of information to provide possibilities by drawing conclusions and taking action to present data in the form of a systematic arrangement of information that is easy to understand.

c. Drawing conclusions

Concluding is the final stage in data analysis which is carried out looking for the results of data reduction and remaining focused on the background of the problem and the goals to be achieved. When a data collection activity is carried out, the writer must look for the meaning of things, cause and effect flow, possible configurations, explanations, patterns, note regularities, and proportions. Initial conclusions that are not yet clear will become more detailed. The conclusion will appear to depend on the size of the collection of field notes,

coding, storage, and retrieval methods to be used, the researcher's skills, and the guidance provided, but sometimes this conclusion is formulated beforehand at the beginning.

RESEARCH RESULTS

To obtain research data, use an observation sheet that has been arranged according to the descriptors obtained. In determining the respondents, the researcher asked the teacher for information with the aim that the researcher focused on 4 respondents. Researchers used observation sheets that focused on children's listening and speaking skills. The results of this research can be seen in the description below:

1. Respondent A

Respondent A, named DN, is a 5-year-old male. DN is a child who is diligent in school and has a neat appearance, and is also a child who is good at making friends, is quiet and if there is something he needs to do then he speaks, DN is also a child who doesn't care about his environment, he just enjoys playing alone. In learning activities, DN is less active and just keeps quiet, When the teacher asks questions he doesn't say anything, and he is even less able to listen to what the teacher is saying.

DN's language skills are still not good, this is indicated by the level of achievement of each descriptor of listening skills and speaking skills with developmental achievements that are not in line with expectations. The developmental achievements of listening skills that have been achieved by DN are being able to distinguish between types of sounds, such as being able to differentiate between the sounds of cows and goats and being able to hear simple sounds such as school bells, Meanwhile, DN's listening skills are still lacking, namely he cannot ask questions clearly, for example if he wants to ask about something he has just seen, so teachers and his friends often don't understand what DN is saying. As for the developmental achievements in speaking skills, DN can say simple sentences such as DN wants to pee.

2. Respondent B

Respondent B, named NY, is a 5-year-old female. NY is a smart child in class, he is a child who is liked by many of his friends because of his friendliness, smiles easily, likes to socialize, and likes to tell stories to his fellow friends. When learning activities in class, NY is also a child who is quite active in class, he can respond to what his teacher says.

NY's language skills are good, this is indicated by the level of achievement of each descriptor of listening skills and speaking skills with developmental achievements that are in line with expectations. As for the listening skill achievement of each descriptor, NY has been able to achieve it well, as well as the speaking skills of each descriptor, NY has been able to achieve it well so that talking to NY is easier than her three friends.

3. Respondent C

Respondent C, named MY, is a 5-year-old female. MY is a good child, quiet in class, but still not very active in studying in class. MY often does not complete the assignments given by the teacher and when asked by the teacher he just keeps quiet, and when asked he is not able to listen to what the teacher is saying, therefore The teacher provides simple body movements so that MY can understand what the teacher is saying to her. MY is often teased by her friends because MY's language skills are not very clear and she often repeats the sentences of the person she is talking to.

MY's language skills are still not good, this is indicated by the level of achievement of each descriptor of listening skills and speaking skills with developmental achievements not being as expected. MY's developmental achievements in listening skills include being able to distinguish types of animal sounds such as cows and goats, and also being able to hear simple sounds such as school bells. Meanwhile, the listening skill that MY has not been able to achieve is that MY has not been able to ask questions clearly to either the teacher or his friends.

4. Respondent D

Respondent D, named DN, is a 5-year-old female. Dian is a good child and very quiet. DN likes to cry if he is asked again by his teacher when he is studying. DN often doesn't focus on paying attention to what his teacher is saying, and his speech is still halting, but DN dares to hang out with his friends.

DN's language skills have begun to develop, this is indicated by the level of achievement of the descriptors of listening skills and speaking skills with developmental achievements that are not as expected. The developmental achievements of listening skills that have been achieved DN include being able to distinguish between types of sounds such as goats and cows, being able to distinguish sounds such as the sound of a bell, being able to ask questions even though the sentences are still stuttering, such as "is that your toy". The development achievements in speaking skills achieved by DN are that the words spoken by DN have reached 1,900 words, Although the pronunciation of the word dian is not very good, and still stammers, the sentences spoken by DN can consist of three words such as "DN wants to have snacks, mother.", Meanwhile, for speaking skills, DN is still not yet able to have a clear dialogue with either his teacher or his friends.

DISCUSSION

Listening Skills

By observing four children, the results obtained were that there were two children whose listening skills were not very good, one child whose listening skills were good, and one child who was starting to do well. Researchers see that there are still children who have difficulty with listening skills and are still unable to grasp the words given by their teacher, such as the teacher telling about a sub-theme that will be discussed. There are still children who don't understand what the teacher is telling them and children also don't understand command sentences. given by the teacher.

This agrees with Fatimah (Rahman,2019) who focuses on the process of paying attention to and listening to verbal symbols, understanding, appreciating, and interpreting to obtain information, capture content, and understand the meaning of communication conveyed by the speaker through speech or spoken language. according to the listening stages according to Coliver (Rahman,2019)

1. Children recognize various sounds through listening and listening,
2. Children can recognize words that sound almost the same,
3. Children can understand commands and apply coordination of these commands,
- 4 Children recognize simple sentences and distinguish correct sentences.

Speaking Skills

By observing four children, the results obtained were that two children's speaking skills were still not good, one child's speaking skills were good, and one child's speaking skills were starting to be good. This can be seen from each descriptor that has been made Researchers saw that there were still children whose speaking abilities were still faltering, and there were children who liked to repeat what their teacher said.

This agrees with Ratnasari (2019), that speaking ability is a skill in the form of oral communication so that you can convey messages and other people can understand what is capable of building social relationships with the environment. This is then supported by the opinion of Jamaris Martin (2014) who states that the language characteristics of children aged 4-5 years are characterized by being able to pronounce more than 1,900 vocabulary words, being able to participate in conversations, being able to listen to other people speaking and responding to conversations.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the results of research conducted on the language skills of children aged 4-5 years at TK Pelangi, it can be concluded as follows:

- 1) Listening skills at TK Pelangi Medan in class A Matahari consisting of 4 respondents, there were 2 children whose listening skills were still not very good, 1 child whose listening skills were very good, and 1 child whose listening skills were starting to be good.
- 2) Speaking skills at TK Pelangi Medan in class A Matahari consisting of 4 respondents, there were 2 children whose speaking skills were still not very good, 1 child whose speaking skills were very good, and 1 child whose speaking skills still stammered when speaking. so often the sentences he utters are not very clear.

Recommendations

The suggestions that researchers can give are:

- 1) For teachers, teachers should continue to train children so that their language skills grow and develop, especially listening skills and speaking skills.

- 2) For the school, the school should collaborate with teachers to see how language skills develop in children aged 4-5 years, where this age is a time to stimulate children's development, especially children's language skills.
- 3) As parents, as parents you should continue to try to stimulate your child's language development and always encourage your child to talk and always correct them if their child's sentences are not good.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

For advanced research, we hope to be able to see or analyze data specifically on children's language skills better so that the visible data becomes clearer, and this research can still be carried out as further research using different analytical techniques and methods so that various results are found for this study.

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